

Data format UV-Vis spectra

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The aim of the following data and metadata format description is to have a standardized scheme for storing UV-vis spectra within the CRC 1411.

During our discussions, we agreed on the following conventions:

- A comment line starts with #.
- The decimal point is a dot.
- The x -data represents the wavelength in nm.
- The scientific notation for all decimal numbers, e.g. 5.364e-6. The number of digits after the decimal point should be constant within a file for readability reasons.
- Only decimals are stored, and percentages should be converted to decimals.
- In cases of multiple measurements, store the averaged data. The white and dark baseline spectra are not stored here. Instead, the information on the baseline type, e.g. the brightness percentages of the baselines, is saved in line 5 of [Figure 1](#).
- The file content is stored in ASCII code (human-readable).
- Each file saved in the following format has the extension `.uvvis`, indicating a structured format for UV-Vis spectra.

Description of the format

In the following, descriptions in curly brackets have to be replaced by specific content. We start with the general part of the file header, and continue with two specifications for the extinction and reflectance data.

Figure 1: General part of file header

```
1 # name of sample: {text}
2 # date of measurement: {yyyy/mm/dd hh:mm:ss (24 hours)}
3 # name of measuring device or file with simulation parameters: {text}
4 # number of measurements averaged: {number}
5 # baseline type: {text}
6 # number of wavelength samples (x-data): {number}
```

Explanation

line 1 Name/identifier of chemical sample or simulation.

line 2 When was the following data collected?

- line 3 Measuring device for assessment of artifacts and presets
or name of file containing simulation parameters for reproducibility
- line 4 How many measurements were used to average the following data values?
- line 5 Description of the baseline type.
- line 6 Extinction (transmission, absorption, extinction cross-section) or reflectance?

Figure 2: Specification for extinction data

```

7 # wavelength in nm      {measured quantity and unit}
8 {x-data}    {y-data}

```

Explanation

- line 7 The x -data is always the wavelength in nm. Examples for the measured quantity: extinction (no unit), extinction cross-section in m^2 .
- line 8 The actual x - and y -data.

Figure 3: Specification for reflectance data

```

7 # number of angle samples (y-data): {integer number}
8 # wavelength in nm vs. angle samples
9 # z-data: {measured quantity and unit}
10           {y-data}
11 {x-data}   {z-data for each angle sample}

```

Explanation

- line 7 The number of angle samples for consistency check; 1 if not angle dependent.
- line 8 What is stored as x - and y -data?
- line 9 What is stored as z -data?
- line 10 Alternation of angle value and standard deviation (SD).
Example: angle_1 SD_1 angle_2 SD_2 ...
- line 11 One x -value followed by reflectance and standard deviation values for each sampled angle, according to labels in previous line.